

A novel ethical analysis of educational XR and AI in literature

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ABSTRACT

This review paper aims to search the landscape of Extended Reality or XReality technology in light of Artificial Intelligence or AI. Through an examination of the Web of Science or WoS, a total of 29 studies were selected for review. We extracted information on the XReality with AI trends in the studies and further classified the pedagogical impact of the studies using the E3XReality framework suggesting that XReality technology may fall into three levels (three Es for XR hence E3XR): 1) Ethics (making sure we do and receive no harm in learning), 2) Educational effectiveness (making sure learning is effective to our goals and outcomes), and 3) Eudaimonia (making sure learning is both effective and ethical). Using open and axial coding, we find that a survey of perceptions or review of the literature was most often made, followed by the study of technical and pedagogical interventions. VR followed by MR was noted the most in the reviewed studies and surprisingly no mention of AR in the silo was made. The use of AI with XReality was mostly done to provide actionable insight, followed by insight and control. The analysis of studies against the conceptual framework E3XReality suggested that current work is largely at the education state and more work is needed to transition to a more sophisticated state of Eudaimonia. Further, several challenges were obtained from the 29 reviewed studies. The contribution of this paper is to offer an extensive synthesis of challenges as well as future recommendations for using XReality with AI in education.

1. Introduction

The goal of this systematic review paper is to provide a comprehensive summary and analysis of using Extended Reality (XReality) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in education. Extended Reality, also known as Cross Reality or XReality is a broad term encompassing reality on a spectrum, namely: Mixed Reality (MR), Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), and everything in between (ScienceDirect, 2023a). AI can be considered as any technology that simulates or builds upon human intelligence, especially using computer systems (ScienceDirect, 2023b).

In education, cross-reality has been shown to improve pedagogy (Guo et al., 2021). The potential is expanding considering AI technologies that can further assist teaching and learning in extended reality environments (Idrees et al., 2022). Despite its potential and versatility, the use of XReality and AI concomitantly has not been extensively investigated in education (Reiners, Davahli, Karwowski, & Cruz-Neira, 2021a, 2021b). Further, educators are reported to know less about the use of technologies such as XReality in education (Roizin & Wang, 2021). These gaps motivate our research to explore the current state and

challenges of employing AI and XReality in education.

In the remainder of this section, we provide background information and review past work on XReality with AI in education. The methods section presents our approach to conducting a review of the literature and the results section shares findings concerning the research questions, namely the state and challenges of incorporating XReality with AI in education. The discussion section gives our analysis of the literature and proposals for future work.

1.1. XReality with AI in education

Artificial intelligence may be considered as the use of technology and theory that their combination leads to artificial ways of thinking, decision-making, and control (Russell & Norvig, 2010). In education, AI has evolved from computer technologies to web-based and online intelligent platforms, to more and more embedded and integrated applications and devices used inside and outside of the classroom with the underlying goal to improve teaching and learning (Chen, Wang, et al., 2020).

AI is expected to address tasks that may be challenging for human

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decision-making or precision such as exam integrity, plagiarism detection, enrollment, transcription of lectures, and student data analysis (University of San Diego, 2023). Further, AI may be advanced to connect campuses, improve the quality of discussion in discussion boards, monitor and tutor for healthy classroom behavior, facilitate communications between students, students, and educational practitioners, and so on (Mills, 2023).

In education, cross-reality is promising to improve teaching and learning both within and outside of the classroom (Ziker et al., 2021). The use of 5G technologies and AI has promoted the state of XReality in education, and coined the term XRED or XReality in Education (Chen et al., 2022). Such technology enables new types of learning environments and experiences and communities of learners and educators. The spectrum of reality includes virtual reality, mixed environment, augmented environment, and real environment (see Fig. 1).

The onset of the pandemic and the need for socially distant and remote education led to advancements in AI and XReality technologies. In online education, for example, it is perceived that extended reality makes education “accessible, effective, engaging, collaborative, self-paced, and adapted to diverse academic trajectories” (p. 1) (Rangel-de Lázaro & Duarte, 2023). Such a perspective might have been effective when students had few teaching and learning alternatives due to the global COVID-19 pandemic. However, with the ease of social restrictions and the return to in-person teaching and learning, the true effect of technologies such as XReality reality is being considered.

While promising many renovations and improvements, AI is also susceptible to use in inappropriate and unethical ways. Subsequently, policy and research efforts have been made to identify, discuss, and address considerations for the use of AI in education. UNESCO’s contributions to the Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education and Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research reports are example efforts aiming to support countries to implement fast actions, plan long-term strategies, and integrate humans in the loop to ensure a human-centered vision of AI technology.

1.2. Theoretical framework

XRED is still a relatively new field and there only exist a few conceptual frameworks about this topic (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Salcedo et al., 2022). In their work, Rauschnabel et al. (2022) aim to provide an updated framework on XR. However, their concern is more about defining the continuum for AR and VR technologies, when this level of detail has not yet been captured extensively in education literature. In education, on the other hand, efforts have been made to create frameworks for either VR or AR technologies in broad terms in certain contexts. Examples include immersive technologies (Korhonen et al., 2022), digital storytelling (Jantakoon et al., 2019), and virtual reality-based learning analytics (Christopoulos et al., 2020). Of the work in education literature, one framework known as the E3XReality (shown in Fig. 2) is more holistic and representative of XReality technology. As shown in Fig. 2 the E3XReality model is comprised of three layers. In the first and most basic level of the model, XReality technology must meet the ethical constraints, at a more advanced and second level of the model, XReality technology needs to promote effective learning. In the third and most sophisticated level of the mode, XReality technology needs to address personalized needs while maintaining effective teaching and ethical constraints.

The goal of this review is to shed light on the current landscape of educational research in the presence of XReality and AI technologies. We

Fig. 2. E3XReality framework adapted from (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021).

recognize that few established frameworks for XReality technologies exist, and frameworks for AI mostly attempt to classify the degree and complexity of intelligence.

Based on our survey of the literature, we aim to review studies and identify if the research design was one of 1) a Survey of perceptions or the literature, 2) a Technical intervention, or 3) a Pedagogical intervention. The first category includes studies that only describe a review of the experiences and perceptions of participants towards XR and AI. The second category includes studies that examine XR and AI through a technical lens such as algorithmic or mathematical conceptions. The third category includes studies that examine XR and AI through pedagogical interventions or simply put teaching and learning practices.

We also examine if the XReality technology was one of: 1) VR, 2) Mixed, and 3) AR. Then we explore if the AI uses with XReality technology was one of 1) Historical insight, 2) Actionable insight, and 3) Insight and control.

Artificial intelligence’s insight may be historical and summarize and analyze an event or context in the past or actionable and provide insight that can be readily used to change an event or context or include both insights and control, in which case the AI not only understands what has happened and needs to happen but also makes adaptive interventions.

Further, we examine if AI and XReality were used in the context of (following E3XReality framework): 1) Ethics, 2) Education, and 3) Eudaimonia. The E3XReality framework (see Fig. 2) helps us to categorize studies done on XReality with AI into:

- Ethics: Research that explores and makes sure we do and receive no harm in learning but does not examine the educational effectiveness aspects
- Education: Research that investigates and makes sure learning is effective for our goals and outcomes but does not examine the ethical aspects
- Eudaimonia: Research that facilitates and makes sure learning is both effective and ethical

Using the E3XReality framework, we differentiate between the levels and consider studies that only address the ethical aspects of education fall in the first or ethics level. We label studies that only address the teaching and learning experience without noting the ethical

Fig. 1. The spectrum of reality is adapted from (Milgram & Kishino, 1994).

considerations that fall in the second or education level. We categorize studies that address both the ethical and educational needs fall in the third or Eudaimonia level.

Understandably, studies that appropriately account for and address the ethical and educational effectiveness concerns have a higher value than studies that only address one of the ethics or educational effectiveness facets. We are thus interested in using the established E3XR framework as a guide to offer further insight into the work done, existing challenges, and future recommendations in a more structured and relevant manner.

1.3. Gap

AI and XReality technology are known to have different goals and origination, yet their combination is rising as an impressive assistive tool (Reiners et al., 2021a, 2021b). Together, AI and XReality can make experiences more immersive, and intelligent. Prior motivations for using AI-XReality uses include 1) training AI, 2) presenting intelligence on XR, and 3) making sense of XR-AI-generated data (Reiners et al., 2021a, 2021b). Yet, the literature denotes various open problems that need

more research by the community. Examples include: investigating the robustness of privacy-preserving methods, developing generalizable explainable and interpretable techniques, and AI-XReality-specific security issues (Qayyum et al., 2022). XReality is considered a tool that can be used for both positive and negative effects, whether on purpose or inadvertently (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021). In education, these challenges may be exacerbated as XReality technology is still not well understood by user groups such as students and teachers. Educators, for example, may not know how to employ the technology or recognize its uses for students to achieve optimal learning (Roizin & Wang, 2021). Such gaps call for taking stock of the work that has been done to date. We present a summary of findings on the current state of education with XReality and AI technologies. Further, we aim to find a comprehensive set of challenges remaining with the use of AI and XReality. The contribution of this work is in providing an extensive synthesis of challenges and future recommendations for the use of XReality with AI in education.

2. Methods

Through a review of the literature, we aim to identify the current

Fig. 3. Title: PRISMA chart.

*Excluded if search terms were not targeted in the title or abstract of the article. **Excluded if the study was focused on specialized industries (e.g., finance, healthcare).

state, challenges, implications, and potential of employing XReality with AI in education. We carried out our search in the comprehensive database Web of Science (WoS). Our inclusion criteria contain studies in English that utilize both AI and XReality in education literature. Exclusion criteria contain studies that are not conducted in English or focus on AI or XReality independently in education.

2.1. Research questions

We seek to examine.

1. How is XReality with AI used in education?
2. What is the reported challenge of XReality with AI in education?

2.2. Search process

An overview of the search process is shown in Fig. 3. The following string was searched in Web of Science or WoS:

(XReality or X reality or extended reality) AND (AI or artificial intelligence) AND (education OR pedagogy OR teaching and learning).

2.3. Methodological framework

Following the grounded theory method of interpretive paradigm, we aim to generalize ideas from the analysis of data presented by the systematic review of the literature (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). We thus do not test a theory against the qualitative data. Instead, we use the data to arrive at findings (Phothongsunan, 2010).

By selecting studies that fit our criteria and classifying the research design, XReality type, AI type, and E3XReality educational classification, we aim to shed light on current trends in this topic and provide insight into current directions. Further, by qualitative thematic analysis of the reported challenges in each reviewed study, we aim to explore present issues and future considerations for the use of XReality with AI in education.

2.4. Search and analysis protocol

We first enter the input string of search in Web of Science or WoS. We download the full records of all the appearing papers in WoS. WoS is considered a comprehensive database we had access to and hence why we used this database for our search. We make a review of the title/abstract and decide on the relevance of each article. We then download each article and evaluate the full text of each article based on relevance. We collect the demographic records of studies selected for review. For charting data, we first search and summarize if the study research design was one of 1) a Survey of perceptions or the literature, 2) Technical intervention, or 3) Pedagogical intervention. We also summarize if XReality technology was one of: 1) VR, 2) Mixed, or 3) AR. We then search and summarize if AI uses with XReality technology was one of 1) Historical insight, 2) Actionable insight, and 3) Insight and control. Historical insight only provides a summary of what has happened in the past, whereas actionable insight can provide more informative information, and students can execute them to correct their learning errors. Actionable insight and control together are the most informative kind of AI by helping the student to both learn about what needs to be revised and is adaptable in the sense of providing insight as student learning evolves. Last, we search and summarize if AI and XReality were used in the context of (following E3XReality framework): 1) Ethics, 2) Education, or 3) Eudaimonia. Further, we extract limitations and future suggestions reported for each study and create a synthesis of future recommendations and challenges in the discussion section based on the full review of each article.

3. Results

The results section shares a synopsis of findings against our research questions, namely.

1. What is the state of XReality with AI use in education?
2. What is the reported challenge of XReality with AI use in education?

3.1. Summary of XReality with AI studies

Of the 29 reviewed studies, the majority focused on exploring user perceptions or sharing the authors' review of a synthesis of prior studies in education. VR technology was most frequently used and the key purpose of XReality use was to make pedagogy more valuable. Further, the AI's key purpose was found to be mostly used for pedagogical and operational purposes. Below we provide details of the findings.

3.1.1. Study topics

Of the 29 reviewed studies, the topic breakdown was as follows.

- 1) Survey of perceptions or the literature ($N = 13$)
- 2) Technical intervention ($N = 11$)
- 3) Pedagogical intervention ($N = 5$)

The most common types of perception studies were reviews and surveys from students, faculty, and users in general. Often the review of the literature and study of perceptions led to understanding unforeseen needs or even the development of new frameworks in the first category of study topics (Survey of perceptions or the literature). In the second category of study topics (Technical intervention), the most common type of technical study was the integration or manipulation of XReality and/or AI technology to improve participation, interaction, and other teaching and learning performance metrics. In the third category of study topics (Pedagogical interventions), the most common type of pedagogical study was using XReality with AI technology to study new mediums of teaching and learning. Contrary to the technical studies, this category did not go deep into the technical modifications and instead focused on the qualitative changes in the learning and teaching space. Examples included the use of XReality technology for creating new learning environments and the adaptation of pedagogical frameworks in the XReality with AI technology for improved teaching and learning.

3.1.2. XReality types

Of the 29 reviewed studies, the XReality type breakdown was as follows.

- 1) VR ($N = 21$)
- 2) MR ($N = 8$)

VR technology was noted to be most used in the reviewed studies and spanned a large space; from actual VR technology and headsets to the use of simulations, applications, and scoring algorithms that strictly operated in a computer-assisted and hence virtual environment. In the first category of XReality types (VR), the notion of VR showed to be rather versatile and often more concerned about computer, cloud, or internet-based student or teacher interaction with their goal-oriented behavior and does not necessarily require a VR headset and VR gear more broadly during teaching and learning experiences.

In the second category of XReality types (MR), studies may have explored the human AI agents' decision-making processes in tandem or attempted to integrate more human-centered design processes or needs in the XReality world. As such the notion of mixed reality in the reviewed studies did not just suffice to the co-existence of AR and VR technology, but more importantly the co-existence and co-evolution of humanistic and technological perspectives and ways of knowing and

doing.

3.1.3. Use of AI

Of the 29 reviewed studies, the use of AI was as follows.

- 1) Historical insight (N = 3)
- 2) Actionable insight (N = 14)
- 3) Insight and control (N = 12)

The most common use of AI with XReality was to provide actionable insight to the learner, teacher, or institution. Taking a step further, 12 studies offered both insight and control over the learning environment and experience. The least used application of AI was to provide historical insight only. The breakdown suggests promising and more sophisticated uses of AI currently being undertaken with XReality technology.

3.1.4. XReality attribution breakdown based on the E3XReality framework

Of the 29 reviewed studies, the XReality attribution breakdown based on the E3XReality framework was as follows.

- 1) Ethics (N = 4)
- 2) Education (N = 18)
- 3) Eudaimonia (N = 7)

The studies focused on ethics explored the needs and requirements for respective humanistic views, decision-making, and reasoning. The studies focused on education examined ways that teaching can become more effective using XReality whereas the studies focused on Eudaimonia took the teaching and learning experience a step further and integrated both the ethical and teaching and learning effectiveness needs. A summary of the reviewed studies is provided in Table 1.

3.2. Summary of AI and XReality use and challenges

Based on our thematic coding and analysis of challenges reported in the reviewed studies, we present the key theme of challenge extracted per study followed (see Table 2) by additional information discussed in each reviewed article (see Table 3 and Table 4).

3.2.1. Key challenges: ethical

The roles and authorities of humans and AI in decision-making are less known: Battistoni et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of not viewing AI in a silo but the interaction effects it may have last on the humans who interact with it. Following Stanton and Jensen’s perspective (Stanton & Jensen, 2020), the authors find that: “the actual trustworthiness of the AI system is influential insofar as it is perceived by the user” (p. 7). And so trust is a function of user insights around their trust towards the technical aspects. With an interest in giving AI the same importance as the user in the design, the authors present a Decision Perception Model to enable adapting to a human-centered design process.

Case-based reasoning (CBR) can still improve: CBR may be considered as the process of new problems based on the solutions of similar problems in the past. Inelmen (2001) shares the utility of using case-based reasoning or CBR which highlights that comparable problems are best solved with comparable solutions. Further, CBR is different from many other AI techniques that are model-based. Emerging from AI And cognitive sciences, CBR is more based on memory than explicit models. Yet CBR also poses challenges. Examples include.

- adaptation which may either be rule-based or focus more on selection (e.g., case subset or feature),
- contrasting cases from stronger sources of data and shifting from vector-based approaches to richer forms.

Table 1
Summary of reviewed studies.

#	Key topic: 1) perception, 2) technical intervention 3) pedagogical intervention	Type 1) AR, 2) VR, 3) MR	Use of AI 1) historical insight 2) actionable insight 3) Insight and control	Level of E3XReality 1) Ethics, 2) Education, 3) Eudaimonia	Reference
1	2) Non-player character	2	1	2	Agrati (2023)
2	2) Object-oriented programming	3	3	2	Alrashidi et al. (2014)
3	2) AI and agent programming techniques to control virtual 3d avatars	2	3	2	Baierle & Gluz (2018)
4	1) How to adapt the human-centered design process	3	3	1	Battistoni et al. (2021)
5	2) Integration of multimodal technologies to tailor individuals’ learning	2	3	3	Bin Qushem et al. (2021)
6	3) Conversational agent able to parse erroneous statements and provide adequate instructions on how to fix them.	2	2	2	Bouali et al. (2019)
7	1) Examined constructs that affect students’ continuous use of VR	2	2	2	Chang et al. (2023)
8	3) A teaching model to provide references for future adaptive online experimental learning	2	1	2	Chen et al. (2020)
9	3) Cognitive immersive language learning environment	2	1	2	Divekar et al. (2022)
10	2) Body-worn VR/AR systems, the triboelectric nanogenerators	3	3	3	Fang et al. (2022)
11	3) AI based on an efficient e-learning framework	2	2	2	Fu et al. (2022)
12	1) Review of the literature and survey of the students	3	2	2	Ilic et al. (2021)
13	1) Case-based reasoning	3	2	1	Inelmen (2001)
14	2) If visitor experiences get enhanced by XR	3	2	2	Jung et al. (2023)
15	1) Review of XReality and AI on online higher ed	3	3	3	Rangel-de Lázaro & Duarte (2023)

(continued on next page)

XReality technology transcends the visual dimension and leads to

Table 1 (continued)

#	Key topic: 1) perception, 2) technical intervention 3) pedagogical intervention	Type 1) AR, 2) VR, 3) MR	Use of AI 1) historical insight 2) actionable insight 3) Insight and control	Level of E3XReality 1) Ethics, 2) Education, 3) Eudaimonia	Reference
16	1) Assessment methods using outcome-based education theory with AI	3	2	2	Lin et al. (2022)
17	1) Review of building information modeling in the context of the metaverse	2	3	2	Liu et al. (2023)
18	1) Use AI-HCI heuristics	2	2	3	Lubin (2022)
19	1) Interactive quantum chemistry	2	3	3	Raucci et al. (2023)
20	1) Review and suggest a metaverse ecosystem	2	2	2	Wang et al. (2022)
21	1) Willingness of faculty to use intelligent tutoring systems in the AI era	2	2	2	Hine (2021)
22	2) Personalized smart education systems using entropy and TOPIS approach	2	2	3	Wang et al. (2023)
23	1) Survey of literature	2	3	1	Wang et al. (2022)
24	2) Application of the XReality enabling human-environment interaction	2	3	2	Xu & Zhang (2022)
25	2) Determining the difficulties of students with dyslexia via VR and AI	2	2	3	Yeguas-Bolívar et al. (2022)
26	2) Intelligent scoring of English composition	2	3	2	Zhang & Yuan (2022)
27	3) Smart education management	2	2	2	Zhang et al. (2023)
28	1) Emotional presentation of users to AI virtual assistants and acceptance	2	2	1	Zhang et al. (2021)
29	2) Automated segmentation of MOOC lectures	2	3	2	Zhang et al. (2016)

virtual behavior: Jung et al. (2023) propose a new variation of Task-Technology Fit following the experience economy model and found a relationship between users' satisfaction when engaging with MR-based experience and the intention to visit back the technology. On the other hand, the purchase intention was significantly related to the actual purchase. As such virtual behavior is integral to user perceptions, learning, and interactions and needs to be studied more carefully.

Social emotions and acceptance are as important as functionality: Zhang et al. (2021) explore the interplay of user perception and

Table 2

Summary of AI and XReality use and challenges in the reviewed studies.

	Key challenges	References
Ethical	The roles and authorities of humans and AI in decision-making are less known. Case-based reasoning can still improve. XReality technologies are subject to change. Social emotions and acceptance are as important as functionality.	Battistoni et al. (2021) Inelmen (2001) Wang et al. (2022) Zhang et al. (2021)
Educational	Expectations are diverse and vary across user groups Pedagogy is greater than technology Pedagogical interactions are missing with AI non-player characters in VR Making virtual agents smart is costly Students need to accept using technology to then learn from it Learning with new technology requires an understanding of how technology works and how to further learning with it Multimodality is still at a generic discourse and not human user level A consistent eLearning experience is missing Multiple criteria must be met for effective learning with AI And XR XReality technology transcends the visual dimension and leads to virtual behavior Sociocultural needs are not necessarily linked with learning indicators in the pedagogy of technology like AI AI and XReality have narrow and perhaps monotonous uses in specialized industries A new digital divide known as the "Metaverse divide" is underway Ethical issues of data AI technologies remain XReality technologies may change based on their mediating technologies Feature extraction is often not fixed or well-understood There are many nooks and crannies for implementing smart education One-size-fits-all may not be helpful in residential education	Agrati (2023) Alrashidi et al. (2014) Baierle & Gluz (2018) Bouali et al. (2019) Chang et al. (2023) Chen et al. (2020) Divekar et al. (2022) Fu et al. (2022) Ilic et al. (2021) Jung et al. (2023) Lin et al. (2022) Liu et al. (2023) Wang et al. (2022) Hine (2021) Xu & Zhang (2022) Zhang & Yuan (2022) Zhang et al. (2023) Zhang et al. (2016)
Eudemonia	Precision education and multimodal technologies need to connect the biological self with sociocultural and other environmental factors There is a need for maturity of technologies Realization of XReality and AI for active learning in online education is needed HCI heuristics need to be revisited in light of technologies such as AI Technologies such as XReality and AI should help overcome or eliminate some resource and competency barriers Lack of clearly defined and effective AI uses in education XReality technologies need to be assistive to users of diverse abilities	Bin Qusheim et al. (2021) Fang et al. (2022) Rangel-de Lázaro & Duart (2023) Lubin (2022) Raucci et al. (2023) Wang et al. (2023) Yeguas-Bolívar et al. (2022)

Table 3

Summary of frequent trends in the reviewed studies.

Most frequent combination	Codes	Frequency
Technical + VR + Actionable Insight + Education	2232	4
Pedagogical + VR + Actionable Insight + Education	3222	3
Perception + VR + Actionable Insight + Education	1222	3
Pedagogical + VR + Historical Insight + Education	3212	2
Perception + MR + Actionable Insight + Education	1322	2
Technical + VR + Actionable Insight + Eudaimonia	2223	2

Table 4
Summary of key challenges in the reviewed studies.

	Key challenges	References
Ethical	Study the sustainability and evolution of roles allocated to humans and technology	Battistoni et al. (2021)
	Compare the impact of different technology uses	Inelmen (2001)
Education	Pay attention to the impact of technology removal on human living	Wang et al. (2022)
	Feelings of learners even novices are valid	Zhang et al. (2021)
	Compare adaptation impact	Agrati (2023)
	Find principal components and correlations between technological, pedagogical, and biological factors	Alrashidi et al. (2014)
	Locate frameworks of interaction	Baierle & Gluz (2018)
	Identify the nature of cost analysis with humans and technology	Bouali et al. (2019)
	See the impact of pedagogical alternatives on user acceptance of technology	Chang et al. (2023)
	Ensure technology does an honest self-branding	Chen et al. (2020)
	Differentiate and account for being of humans versus technology	Divekar et al. (2022)
	Focus on consistency in learning experiences	Fu et al. (2022)
	Learning is consistent and understood even if distributed	Ilic et al. (2021)
	Account for the impact of extended reality in real-life living	Jung et al. (2023)
	Prevent a business-driven educational climate	Lin et al. (2022)
	Make inaccuracies or trivializations in extended reality clear	Liu et al. (2023)
	Emphasize equity of experience with technology for all	Wang et al. (2022)
	Recognize there are many unknown blind spots with the use of educational technology	Hine (2021)
	Pedagogy with technology is dependent on technological components, from large to small	Xu & Zhang (2022)
	Technology-proposed features may not make sense to humans	Zhang & Yuan (2022)
	More aggressive technology integration is not the key	Zhang et al. (2023)
Both one-size-fits-all and personalized learning comes with risks	Zhang et al. (2016)	
Eudemonia	Examine the impact on both the subjective and measurable human attributes	Bin Qusheem et al. (2021)
	Make technological advancement dependent on human and not technological ability	Fang et al. (2022)
	Connect active learning between real and extended reality environments	Rangel-de Lázaro & Duarte (2023)
	Account for the evolution of human-centered heuristics and interactions	Lubin (2022)
	Be wary about full control allocation to and acceptance of technology	Raucci et al. (2023)
	Acknowledge that any assortment of technology comes with both benefits and consequences	Wang et al. (2023)
	Abilities are diverse even for abled-bodied	Yeguas-Bolívar et al. (2022)

performance. The findings of their study showed that there is much emotional complexity towards the use of AI virtual assistants with high dependence on perceptions of trust.

3.2.2. Key challenges: educational

Expectations are diverse and vary across user groups: Agrati (2023) examines AI as an enhancement to metaverse interaction performance through an analysis of large data in real-time. The author found that different educators (e.g., student-teachers and school tutors) have different expectations from using the metaverse and the new roles the metaverse may create such as the non-player character involved in

teaching and learning.

Pedagogy is greater than technology: Alrashidi et al. (2014) borrow the perspective of Brad Cox and consider AI as a key component of object-oriented programming (Cox, 1986); “an object-oriented program is structured as a community of acting agents, called objects. Each object has a role to play. Each object provides a service, or performs an action, that is used by other members of the community.” (p. 9). The authors reflect on the importance of recognizing pedagogical layers as opposed to mere computational layers and understanding the interplay of technology use with human mechanisms of teaching and learning, Pedagogical interactions are missing with AI non-player characters in VR: Baierle and Gluz (2018) explore the use of AI to introduce NPCs or non-player characters as a way to artificially represent the external users or avatars and control them. The authors critique the lack of interaction within the VR environment with intelligent pedagogical NPCs specifically in a natural language.

Making virtual agents smart is costly: Bouali et al. (2019) explore the role of adding AI or AI as a conversational agent in a VR game that teaches object-oriented programming (OOP). The agent is intended to provide teaching and learning support such as parsing erroneous statements and providing feedback on them. The author’s current work does not explore the use of smart agents as the authors find this requires the use of more sophisticated technology and pedagogical design.

Students need to accept using a technology to then learn from it: Chang et al. (2023) explore student perceptions towards constant use of VR using the Technology Acceptance Theory (TAM) theory. This theory postulates that the acceptance of technology is predicted by behavioral intention which is determined by the perception of technology’s usefulness and ease of use. Prior work suggests that perceptions may be impacted by several factors, among them being artificial intelligence. In this work, the students learned about English and performed problem-solving tasks, which comprised three multiple-choice questions using action keywords, vocabulary, and expressions. The findings of the control experiment suggest that the traditional teaching method had lower scores than VR on Action Keywords and Vocabulary.

Learning with new technology requires an understanding of technology and how to further learning with it: Chen, Chen, and Lin (2020) perceive the main contribution of AI assistants to be data collection and intelligent analysis. Examples include data from students watching instructional videos, carrying out experiments, personal knowledge graph structures of students developed from experimental reports, topics identified to be difficult for students, and engagement (e.g., homework) information. The authors find students often spend too much time on the debugging time portion and receive very few hints. Their work thus offers a medium to summarize student performance and guide them to problem-solving.

Multimodality is still at a generic discourse and not human user level: Divekar et al. (2022) endorse the use of AI with XReality in foreign language education such that experiential learning comes to emulate international immersion programs. The authors propose a Cognitive Immersive Language Learning Environment which engages learners in non-dyadic multimodal conversations for learning Chinese as a foreign language. The XReality provides a visual setting to the students while the AI provides opportunities to enact conversations inside the visual setting. In this context, AI is perceived as multimodal as the ability to observe, listen, talk, and present conversational topics for shopping in the streets of China. As such the multimodal aspects were largely rooted at a discourse level and did not necessarily understand how the human learner was behaving and feeling in real time.

A consistent eLearning experience is missing: Fu et al. (2022) propose an AI-based Efficient E-learning Framework (AI-EELF). The authors find there is a challenge to improve course supplies, student learning style projection, teaching value, and service support and implement e-learning in China’s higher education system.

Multiple criteria must be met for effective learning with AI And XR: Ilic et al. (2021) evaluate the literature and analyze the potentials of AI,

machine learning, and XReality environments in higher education. The authors find that AI and ML are influenced by students' skills on these topics, the collaborative learning environment, and an available research environment for researchers. These three key factors, however, may not be always achievable.

Sociocultural needs are not necessarily linked with learning indicators in the pedagogy of technology like AI: [Lin et al. \(2022\)](#) suggest refining the teaching aims of overview to AI (AI) course and integrating ideological and political elements, and establishing a corresponding relationship with the completion indicators reinforced by the course. Yet, at present, ideological and political education (IPE) courses in universities do not meet the need for talent training.

AI and XReality have narrow and perhaps monotonous uses in specialized industries: [Liu et al. \(2023\)](#) explore the research development and tendencies of immersive technology-driven Building Information Modeling or BIM applications. The authors find that the knowledge of specific opportunities and ways for incorporating immersive technologies into building process workflows remains fragmented and inadequate. Their review of literature informs six clusters of relationships between immersive technologies and BIMs namely VR, Internet of Things (IoT), Digital Twin, 3D models, design, and AR. The six mark the research hotspots research tendencies of immersive technology-driven BIM.

A new digital divide known as the "Metaverse divide" is underway: [Wang, Yu, et al. \(2022\)](#) find that the metaverse which is fabricated on new and arising technologies such as extended reality and AI is the third and most recent wave of the internet revolution. Through a review of the literature, the authors suggest a framework with four major hubs, namely: 1) instructional design and performance technology hub; 2) knowledge hub; 3) research and technology hub; and 4) talent and training hub. The authors warn that the many technological developments supporting the metaverse world may in turn lead to a digital divide known as the "Metaverse divide".

Ethical issues of data AI technologies remain: [Hine \(2021\)](#) reviews the literature and finds several ethical issues to remain with the use of data-driven technologies such as AI. Examples include: a fragmented and slender examination of human subjects research at the university level, interference of academic and commercial goals, and lack of inclusivity especially of laypeople and technical voices.

XReality technologies are subject to change: [Wang, Yu, et al. \(2022\)](#) find that movement management can be linked with AI. For example, Mobile edge computing or MEC as a distributed computing model can offload tasks that are intensive on the competition side to the edge of the network. The authors provide a thorough survey of the Metaverse that is MEC-based. A particular emphasis is given to the technology's union, designs, and application settings, e.g., CloudXReality and BoundlessXR. BoundlessXR, for example, offers more immersive mobile XReality experiences with photorealistic visuals via split rendering and fast connectivity.

XReality technologies may change based on their mediating technologies: [Xu and Zhang \(2022\)](#) find that the addition of XR, AI, holographic technology, and VR cooperatively enables new learning spaces.

Feature extraction is often not fixed or well understood: [Zhang and Yuan \(2022\)](#) propose an automatic English composition grading model by AI and ML from the lens of natural language processing. The authors find that the prediction of performance may be examined based on the number of features that may not be fixed or well understood.

Many nooks and crannies for implementing smart education: [Zhang et al. \(2023\)](#) find that the application of AI to the smart education administration mechanism is still a challenge. While education can be greatly enhanced in the presence of AI. This could be partly due to the many places in which smart technology can be used and the lack of knowledge on its short- and long-term impact. In their work, for example, the authors focus on merging intelligent self-powered sensors and deep learning methods to offer a face recognition representation with improved multi-level feature fusion.

One-size-fits-all may not be helpful in residential education: [Zhang et al. \(2016\)](#) endorse the use of videos that are structured and allow non-linear navigation as well as offer learners various needs to find the needed information efficiently.

3.2.3. Key challenges: eudemonia

Precision education and multimodal technologies need to connect the biological self with sociocultural and other environmental factors: [Qusheh et al. \(2021\)](#) use the potential of AI for adaptivity features in immersive environments. Examples of prior research include path-finding, adaptive game engine, role-playing elements, dynamic difficulty adjustment, macro-adaptivity, non-player character behavior, an adaptation of challenge order, and selection. In this work, however, the authors suggest the use of AI and multimodal technology in ways that spot and connect the multidimensional nature of learners and learning.

There is a need for maturity of technologies: [Fang et al. \(2022\)](#) explore a type of VR/AR system worn on the body, namely the triboelectric nanogenerators (TEGs). Using AI with TEGs may enable the differentiation of difficult movement patterns in areas such as remote sensing, human-machine interactions, and wearable robotics control. The authors find several challenges in using such technology. Examples include challenges of device optimization, establishing standard fabrication processes, needing a multi-channel or large number of TEGs, and multimodal interaction depending on beyond mechanical stimulation (e.g., sensations that are multimodal).

Realization of XReality with AI for active e-learning is needed: [Rangel-de Lázaro and Duart \(2023\)](#) find that XReality with AI technologies can be available toolboxes to strengthen an active and learner-centered teaching method. They find the technologies can impact learner agency and outcomes, and make online education more accessible and effective to varied academic trails.

HCI heuristics need to be revisited in light of technologies such as AI: [Lubin \(2022\)](#) criticizes that User Interface or UI and Experience Designers or XD lack the necessary understanding of AI and lack principles for everyday design activities. The authors share a six-category AI-HCI heuristic that covers categories such as Human Factors/Ergonomics, Accessibility, User Consent, Privacy by Design, User Controls/Affordances, and Transparency.

Technologies such as XReality with AI should help overcome or eliminate some resource and competency barriers: [Raucci et al. \(2023\)](#) find that technologies such as AI have greatly contributed to developing and solving quantum chemistry algorithms and accurately predicting properties (e.g., molecular) that are effective for chemists. Yet mainstream use has not been achieved, mainly because there needs to be domain expertise, skills such as computer programming, and computer hardware that are powerful. The authors share that some of these needs may be met and even eliminated using cutting-edge technologies.

Lack of clearly defined and effective AI uses in education: [Wang et al. \(2023\)](#) share that AI in education has been rapidly developing over thirty years, yet educators may remain unsure about its appropriate pedagogical use. Their review of the literature shows that the best and most reliable parts of a smart education system contain smart devices, AI, and ML technologies.

XReality technologies need to be assistive to users of diverse abilities: [Yeguas-Bolívar et al. \(2022\)](#) share that Dyslexic students have problems with reading, memorizing, and uncovering concepts. Yet the severity of these challenges may be relieved through both therapies and the creation of compensatory mechanisms. For example, a mobile application can integrate VR to collect data quickly and easily, and artificial intelligence-based software can be used to analyze the collected data for customizing the supporting methodology for each student.

4. Discussion

4.1. Key findings against the literature

Of the 29 reviewed studies a survey of perceptions or review of the literature was most often made, followed by the study of technical and pedagogical interventions. It may seem ironic that technology integrations into education are less examined through a technical research design and more of a perceptual approach. Yet, this duality may signify the importance and role of our experiences with technology. Hence it is anticipated that as these technologies evolve more analysis of humans' perceptions and experiences with technology emerge. A gap may thus become how to best align and link the technology with humanistic experiences and outcomes.

VR followed by MR was noted the most in the reviewed studies and surprisingly no mention of AR in the silo was made. This could be because, from a safety standpoint, VR technology may require less gate movement like walking making it a safer option to include. MR, as the name suggests provides the highest level of variety in terms of realities. Yet it seems strange that both MR and VR environments dominate, and few AR environments are studied. This may change with technological advancements making the use of AR technology such as AR glasses safer to use. The use of AI with XReality was mostly done to provide actionable insight, followed by insight and control. The much smaller number of studies using AI just for historical insight and the higher number of studies on actionable insight or insight and control may suggest the advancement of AI with XReality in this field. The analysis of studies against the conceptual framework proposed by X suggested that current work is largely at the education state and more work is needed to transition to a more sophisticated state of Eudaimonia. Further, a great deal of challenges were obtained from the 29 reviewed studies.

When exploring the research design XR, AI, and E3XReality (see [Table 1](#) for codes) in tandem, we find a few emergent patterns rising from the reviewed studies. A summary of the frequent trends in the reviewed studies is presented in [Table 3](#). The summary shows that current research may be perhaps stale at mostly using VR technology to provide actionable insight, rather than insight and control and address the needs of educational effectiveness, missing out on providing both enhanced educational experiences and meeting ethical needs. Future work can thus aim to focus more on studying extended reality through broader means and include AR and MR as well in contexts that lead to actionable insight and control and fulfill learner flourishing leading to Eudaimonia.

4.2. Proposed implications

Having different user expectations from the XReality devices is most likely probable ([Agrati, 2023](#)). It may be necessary to harmonize the expectations by educating learners and educators on why an XReality device is designed with a set configuration. For example, non-player characters introduce external users or avatars not controlled by the human player ([Baierle & Gluz, 2018](#)). The AI technology may enable control of NPC characters through objectives set by the course. Such interactions may be considered unique as they may not be shaped by adaptive inputs and interactions between the NPC and human players. Such forms of AI may thus be considered less adaptive to the contest and more reliant on the goals and objectives set external to the human player/learner. An alternative approach is to accept learning paths and outcomes for learners are different depending on their needs and abilities ([Yeguas-Bolívar et al., 2022](#); [Zhang et al., 2016](#)). Such technology may in turn lead to students gaining different sets of learning outcomes from each experience, contributing to their unique individual journeys as opposed to a set level of course learning outcomes.

A recognition of pedagogical changes, as opposed to mere technological changes and postulations in the development of extended AI technology in education, is needed ([Alrashidi et al., 2014](#)). It is known

that sociocultural needs are not necessarily linked with the often highly technical indicators in the pedagogy of XReality with AI technology ([Lin et al., 2022](#)). This may be achieved through design-based approaches that aim to connect pedagogical theories, goals, and outcomes with technological manipulations more directly. There is a need for multi-modal technologies to connect the biological self with sociocultural and other environmental factors ([Qushem et al., 2021](#); [Divekar et al., 2022](#)). As a result, our notion of learning styles may expand to include dimensions of teaching and learning with environmental contexts and state of emotions, physical attributes, and overall beings of the learner. What makes decision-making challenging perhaps is that the allocation of roles and authorities between humans and AI for decision-making is less known ([Battistoni et al., 2021](#)) and clearly defined example uses ([Wang et al., 2023](#)). AI and humans each may have their own discourse to decision making. When the intelligence combine and interact with one another, each needs to find a delicate balance between learning about the other's decision-making mechanisms and competing for a state where their needs are best met.

Technologies such as XReality and AI should help overcome or eliminate some resource and competency barriers ([Raucci et al., 2023](#)). Still, making the virtual agent to be smart and right at all times is costly ([Bouali et al., 2019](#)). We find there may be too high of expectations from smart technology, given that the alternative would be a human teacher with limited memory and learning capacity. The use of adaptive technology may save time and costs by making technologies smart based on human teachers' or learners' learning errors and abilities. Another contributing factor in the use of XReality and AI technologies may be achieved when users fully trust and understand such technologies ([Chang et al., 2023](#); [Chen, Wang, et al., 2020](#); [Fang et al., 2022](#); [Zhang et al., 2021](#)). Such acceptance opens concerns at various levels, from the changes in the triad (i.e., body, mind, environment) embodiment of the human learner to the ethical and epistemological issues around the being of humans. Most notably, there is an equal likelihood for humans to become more of a technology, as opposed to technology becoming more of a human. Such an effect may in turn morph humans into beings with new and unanticipated sets of challenges and needs.

XReality and AI technology are more readily useable in online and technology-dependent settings. A variety of technology may be used leading to a variety of learning environments and experiences ([Zhang et al., 2023](#)). Fundamentally institutions emphasize using such technology to promote more active learning among students ([Rangel-de Lázaro & Duarte, 2023](#)). Yet, institutions are concerned about the e-learning and technology-dependent experiences and learning outcomes can be consistent among learners ([Fu et al., 2022](#)). This challenge is heightened by the precursor of needing multiple criteria to be met for effective learning with AI and XReality ([Ilic et al., 2021](#)) and the likelihood of updates and changes to technology being on the horizon ([Wang, Yu, et al., 2022](#); [Xu & Zhang, 2022](#)).

The broadest challenge remaining with the XReality and AI technologies is in recognizing, preventing, or mitigating ethical issues ([Hine, 2021](#)). Efforts need to be made to prevent or address technological divides ([Wang, Yu, et al., 2022](#)). Further, HCI heuristics need to be revisited in light of technologies such as XReality and AI ([Lubin, 2022](#)). As such a deeper understanding of XReality and AI technology is needed. First and foremost, XReality technology transcends the visual dimension and leads to virtual behavior ([Jung et al., 2023](#)). One solution to this is to develop and extensively study only narrow and perhaps monotonous uses of such technology in specialized industries ([Liu et al., 2023](#)). An example is case-based reasoning, where attempts to solve similar problems are best solved with similar solutions ([Inelmen, 2001](#)). Doing so may help avoid some of the challenges in model-based approaches such as feature extraction that are often not fixed or well understood ([Zhang & Yuan, 2022](#)). An alternative approach is to develop and extensively study a broad range of uses of technology but in a less extensive manner. Doing so can help us gain a more comprehensive understanding of the effect of technology on our professional and personal learning

experiences and lives.

4.3. Considerations for challenges

We acknowledge that our study comes with limitations. Only studies in the Web of Science were considered for this review. Further, our string of searches noted the term XReality or extended reality, so we did not search for VR, AR, or MR studies with AI specifically. Based on the review of 29 studies, we suggest the following areas for future work for XReality technologies that make use of AI:

Based on our thematic coding and analysis of results and challenges extracted from the reviewed studies, we present the key theme of future work (see [Table 2](#) and [Table 4](#)) followed by a discussion.

4.3.1. Ethical

Study the sustainability and evolution of roles allocated to humans and technology: Create an understanding of role allocation, sustainability of roles, and changes to roles and acceptance from both the human and AI sides.

Compare the impact of different technology uses: Observe the impact of model-based versus more memory-based paradigms of AI and their impact on student learning and retention.

Pay attention to the impact of technology removal on human living: A big challenge in human users' interaction with technologies such as XReality and AI may be found when the technology is removed and how the learner behaves in the real environment as an aftermath. What may make this adaptation even more difficult is the many changes and updates the technology may be subject to leading to discontinuity of skill development with a technology from the human user side.

Feelings of learners even novices are valid: Technology may have a better idea of where the student stands and what their errors are but may not necessarily understand what the student is going through and how much toll the processing has on the learner. There is thus a need to recognize and account for learners' feelings and well-being (e.g., avoiding motion sickness) when using technology.

4.3.2. Education

Compare adaptation impact: Consider studying and comparing the impact of human (e.g., learner or educator) adaptation to AI and vice versa. Ensure the study is done in a controlled manner. Compare how more of human adaptation to technology compares to more of technology adaptation to humans. See what impact there is if the control is fully given to one entity versus divided up 50/50.

Find principal components and correlations between technological, pedagogical, and biological factors: Examine the principal components and correlate technological interventions with pedagogical constructs. Such examination may benefit from using both biological and subjective measurement approaches. The goal of such studies is to find the best fitting or correlating technological with pedagogical and biological constructs.

Locate frameworks of interaction: Create a framework of pedagogical interactions between humans and AI. Account for the advantages, drawbacks, and ethical considerations of each interaction.

Identify the nature of cost analysis with humans and technology: Develop cost analysis or other analytical frameworks for deciding on the use times and types of AI technology such as virtual agents.

See the impact of pedagogical alternatives on user acceptance of technology: Detach pedagogical evaluations (e.g., grades, etc.) to find if there are any changes to the acceptance of XReality and AI technology use. Create a climate where students can feel the technology provides a psychologically and physically safe learning environment through practices such as the delivery of constructive feedback and promotion of motivation.

Ensure technology does an honest self-branding: Make AI and XReality technology self-explanatory in a non-biased educational and non-financially driven way. This may require not allowing the

technology and its brand to aggrandize or underscore their impact.

Differentiate and account for being of humans versus technology: Recognize that the way technology may "see", "hear", "speak" or "show" learning are fundamentally different from the humans. Note that humans may set the initial conditions and be somewhat the originators of AI but not necessarily the gatekeepers and moderators of AI as time goes by. AI has the power to develop and expand more rapidly than humans. It is thus important to not model AI in ways that would lead humans (learners or teachers) to feel they are always participating in a losing game.

Focus on consistency in learning experiences: Discontinuity and abrupt changes in learners' experiences may cause more damage than good for the user. Learning experiences should thus be consistent not only between humans but within the tasks of a human.

Learning not consistent and understood even if distributed: Focus on universal learning institutions, accessible resources for pedagogy and research to make AI and XReality facets of educational organizations more connected and comparable.

Account for the impact of extended reality in real-life living: Study the challenges of continuous virtual behavior on real and purely physical behavior. Examine the impact on the social nature of humans and best practices to not disturb the real embodiment of humans.

Prevent a business-driven educational climate: Ensure that learning is not sacrificed or discriminated against by the strength of technology and the monopolized educational industry. Address sociocultural gaps and not add to them by introducing such technologies.

Make inaccuracies or trivializations in extended reality clear: There needs to be high attention paid to ensuring real environments and contexts such as civil structures are accurately modeled with technologies such as XReality and AI. For example, students working with civil structures with XReality and AI need to be provided with a realistic environment and any trivializations need to be made clear, so the students account for the blind spots hidden by the technology in real physical settings.

Emphasize equity of experience with technology for all: If education fates are in the hands of big educational corporations, there is a high likelihood of monopolization and a digital divide created among human user groups and social classes. Institutions have the delicate role of ensuring services are uniformly presented and consistently support all types of demographic groups.

Recognize there are many unknown blind spots with the use of educational technology: The landscape and requirements for human-subject research with technologies such as XReality and AI need to change and be revamped to account for the many blind spots where ethics may be violated at both technical and pedagogical and sociocultural levels.

Pedagogy with technology is dependent on technological components, from large to small: It is important to keep track of technology's components and their effect on education. The more parts a technology has, the higher the likelihood that its course of progress would be interdependent on more factors.

Technology-proposed features may not make sense to humans: Humans and technology perceive and classify the world in different ways. Technologies are more computational and mathematical, whereas humans are more linguistic, and discourse driven. While technologies may do an accurate and comprehensive job in making feature selections, humans may fall short in understanding them or attributing them to their lives.

More aggressive technology integration is not the key: Research designs may be tempted to use technology in a broader variety of ways in an intervention with the hope of gaining a statistically significant difference. Such attempts may be considered poor since untangling the impacting variable may become almost impossible.

Both one-size-fits-all and personalized learning comes with risks: Students need to deal with the pedagogical experience that is presented to them. Both one-size-fits-all and personalized learning create

disturbances for the learner, especially if the learner was practicing the opposite beforehand.

4.3.3. Eudemonia

Examine the impact on both the subjective and measurable human attributes: Study the role of different factors (e.g., context and environment, level of AI integration, etc.) on both the biological and subjective well-being of humans. Consider interaction effects as they may largely affect outcomes even if kept controlled from one case to another.

Make technological advancement dependent on human and not technological ability: The maturity of technology should be subject to the needs and abilities of the human users who wish to benefit from the interaction with the technology. The maturity of technology should thus not be subject to previous technologies only and without paying attention to the human capacity.

Connect active learning between real and extended reality environments: Examine the impact of students' active learning in virtual versus physical spaces. Find ways to connect the two through safely orchestrated AR environments.

Account for the evolution of human-centered heuristics and interactions: The heuristics of human-centered design may change in light of each of XReality with AI. The mix of the two technologies may make the development of heuristics more sophisticated and complex. This could be because each entity (I.e., human, XR, and AI) may carry over their perceptions of human-centered heuristics and their interaction may lead to conflicts or amplified concerns in HCI.

Be wary about full control allocation to and acceptance of technology: High reliance on technology only to solve complex problems that are not second nature to humans should be taken with a grain of salt. This is because if humans are unaware of the inner workings of the problem-solving of AI and XR, they are also likely to be unaware of their outcomes and repercussions.

Acknowledge that any assortment of technology comes with both benefits and consequences: The most widely used technologies such as AI and ML may be more often under scrutiny. Yet, a blueprint is needed to classify and compare all assortments of smart technologies in education and offer an intuitive understanding of where they are best used and ways in which their use can cause concern.

Abilities are diverse even for abled-bodied: The use of technology causes new notions of ability and disability. Such notions may transcend the current definitions given that even abled-bodied humans would face different sets of abilities and disabilities with the use of technologies such as XReality and AI.

5. Conclusion

The goal of this review paper is to provide an overview of the landscape of Extended Reality or XReality technology in light of AI or AI. Through a search of Web of Science or WoS, a total of 29 studies were selected for review. We extracted information on the XReality AI trends in the studies and further classified the pedagogical impact of the studies using the E3XReality framework suggesting that XReality technology may fall into three levels: 1) Ethics, 2) Educational effectiveness, and 3) Eudaimonia comprising both ethics and personalized educational effectiveness. We present a summary of findings on the current state of education with XReality and AI technologies. Further, a great deal of challenges were obtained from the 29 reviewed studies. The contribution of this work is in providing an extensive synthesis of challenges and future recommendations for the use of XReality with AI in education.

6. Statements on open data and ethics

Data sharing does not apply to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bahar Memarian: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tenzin Doleck:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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